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Digitalization and institutional trust as factors in countering shadow activities of Ukrainian enterprises and stimulating foreign investment

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***Abstract.** The relevance of the study stems from the growing importance of digital transformations and institutional trust as key factors in shaping the investment environment. In modern conditions, even a developed digital infrastructure does not guarantee capital inflows in the absence of trust in state and market institutions. At the same time, sustainable trust is not formed outside of transparent digital processes that reduce transaction costs and ensure the predictability of decisions.*

The purpose of the article is to theoretically and practically substantiate the relationship between digitalization and institutional trust as key factors of a favorable investment climate, as well as to identify scientifically verified approaches to increasing the investment attractiveness of the national economy.

The research methodology was based on a combination of systemic and comparative analysis, an institutional approach and generalization of international experience. Structural and functional analysis methods were used to identify the role of digital tools in reducing risks, as well as economic and statistical techniques to illustrate the impact of institutional trust on the dynamics of investment flows.

Research has shown that digitalization provides transparency, speed, and accessibility of economic processes; however, its effect is significantly reduced in conditions of a deficit of institutional trust. It was established that trust in state and market institutions without digital mechanisms of openness cannot form a predictable environment for investors. It was proven that only their combination creates a new quality of the investment climate, where digital technologies become guarantees of stability, and trust - a tool for reducing risks.

Thus, the combination of digitalization and trust in institutions determines the effectiveness of the functioning of the investment climate, ensuring predictability, risk reduction and stability of capital inflows. The main barriers limiting the synergistic impact of digitalization and institutional trust on investment processes are identified: fragmentation of digital infrastructure, legal uncertainty, unequal access of businesses to digital services and high cyber risks. It is proposed to create a single digital ecosystem of government and business services, improve the legal framework, and strengthen cyber protection mechanisms. Prospects for further research include the quantitative measurement of the integrated impact of digitalization and trust on investment processes, the development of indicators of their combination, and the adaptation of international practices to national conditions.

Keywords: *digital transformation, transparency, institutional stability, investment climate, transaction costs, economic trust, competitiveness.*

Цифровізація та інституційна довіра як чинники протидії тіньовій діяльності українських підприємств і стимулювання зовнішніх інвестицій

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***Анотація.** Актуальність дослідження зумовлено зростаючим значенням цифрових трансформацій та інституційної довіри як визначальних чинників формування інвестиційного середовища. У сучасних умовах навіть розвинена цифрова інфраструктура не гарантує припливу капіталу за відсутності довіри до державних і ринкових інститутів. Водночас стійка довіра не формується поза прозорими цифровими процесами, які знижують транзакційні витрати та забезпечують передбачуваність рішень.*

Мета статті полягає у теоретичному та практичному обґрунтуванні взаємозв'язку цифровізації та інституційної довіри як ключових факторів сприятливого інвестиційного клімату, а також у визначенні науково вивірених підходів до підвищення інвестиційної привабливості національної економіки.

Методологія дослідження ґрунтується на поєднанні системного та порівняльного аналізу, інституційного підходу та узагальнення міжнародного досвіду. Було застосовано методи структурно-функціонального аналізу для виявлення ролі цифрових інструментів у зниженні ризиків, а також економіко-статистичні підходи для ілюстрації впливу інституційної довіри на динаміку інвестиційних потоків.

Встановлено, що цифровізація забезпечує прозорість, швидкість і доступність економічних процесів, проте її ефект значно знижується за умов дефіциту інституційної довіри. Показано, що довіра до державних і ринкових інститутів без цифрових механізмів відкритості не здатна формувати прогнозоване середовище для інвесторів. Доведено, що лише їхня синергія створює нову якість інвестиційного клімату, де цифрові технології перетворюються на гарантії стабільності, а довіра – на інструмент зниження ризиків.

Узагальнено, що поєднання цифровізації та довіри до інститутів визначає ефективність функціонування інвестиційного клімату, забезпечуючи передбачуваність, зниження ризиків та стабільність надходження капіталу. Виявлено основні бар'єри, що обмежують синергійний вплив цифровізації та інституційної довіри на інвестиційні процеси: фрагментарність цифрової інфраструктури, правова невизначеність, нерівний доступ бізнесу до цифрових сервісів та високі кіберризики. Запропоновано створення єдиної цифрової екосистеми державних і бізнес-послуг, удосконалення правового поля та посилення механізмів кіберзахисту.

Перспективи подальших досліджень вбачаються у кількісному вимірюванні інтегрованого впливу цифровізації та довіри на інвестиційні процеси, розробленні індикаторів їхньої синергії та адаптації міжнародних практик до національних умов.

Ключові слова: *цифрова трансформація, прозорість, інституційна стабільність, інвестиційний клімат, транзакційні витрати, економічна довіра, конкурентоспроможність.*

Problem statement. The formation of a favorable investment environment in modern conditions increasingly depends on the level of digitalization of economic processes and institutional trust, which ensures the stability and predictability of the

functioning of social relations. The problem is that even with a developed digital infrastructure, investment activity decreases if there is no trust in state institutions. At the same time, institutional trust cannot be formed outside the context of digital transparency, which guarantees openness of information flows, efficiency of decision-making and reduction of transaction costs. It necessitates the search for the optimal balance between technological transformations and strengthening trust in state and market institutions, which is essential both in the scientific dimension and in the practical provision of sustainable economic development. The scientific significance of the problem lies in identifying systemic relationships between digital transformations and trust in institutions that determine the effectiveness of investment flow management. The practical value of the study lies in the possibility of forming comprehensive state policy strategies on this basis, aimed at increasing investment attractiveness. It is of direct importance for economic growth, integration into global markets, and ensuring the country's competitiveness.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. Scientific research on the relationship between digitalization and institutional trust in creating a favorable investment environment can be categorized into four areas. The first area covers the institutional foundations of investment activity. O. Sukhoveyev substantiates systemic approaches to assessing investment activity, taking into account digital indicators of transparency and speed of information flows [1]. I. Mishchuk and co-authors prove that the institutional environment of innovation activity acquires modernization potential only in combination with digital integration mechanisms [2]. B. Torbych emphasizes the importance of institutional support for attracting investment by Ukrainian enterprises, where digital tools enhance the level of trust in the legal system [3]. The generalization of this direction shows that digitalization serves as a basis for strengthening the institutional base of investments; however, further research requires the unification of the methodology for assessing digital factors in relation to trust in institutions.

The second direction focuses on the transparency and efficiency of investment processes. T. Shpomer and co-authors demonstrate that digital technologies provide a new level of transparency and reduce corruption risks in the interaction between investors and state structures [4]. L. G. Kvasnii and R. Yu. Hrytsko analyze the legal principles of forming an integrated investment climate, emphasizing the need for digital mechanisms to harmonize legal norms with the requirements of the economy [5]. D. Vasylykivskyi and V. Vyshniuk find that the mechanism for attracting foreign investment is effective only if digital transparency tools are implemented that build trust in national regulators [6]. This body of work demonstrates that digitalization enhances transparency and legal certainty; however, further research should prioritize the development of practical indicators to measure digital transparency in investment processes.

The third direction is devoted to environmental, technological and corporate trust strategies. Q. Guo and co-authors emphasize that green digitalization stimulates environmental innovation, but its effectiveness depends on institutional pressure and the level of trust in environmental standards [7]. M. F. Mubarak and M. Petraite show that Industry 4.0 technologies can ensure open innovation only if there is digital trust as a basis for partnerships [8]. M. J. Lee and co-authors prove that institutional pressures, combined with the digital capabilities of companies, shape the effectiveness of ESG strategies, affecting economic, social and environmental outcomes [9]. In summary, this direction shows that digitalization and institutional trust interact as a dual driver of sustainable development, but further research should study the integration of digital solutions into corporate and environmental strategies, taking into account regulatory constraints.

The fourth direction covers the cultural and social aspects of digital trust. Y. Liu and co-authors prove that the financial digitalization of companies directly affects the quality of internal management and social trust, creating a basis for investment stability [10]. M. Natsvaladze emphasizes the importance of new

institutional economics to explain the role of digitalization in reducing transaction costs and shaping the predictability of interactions [11]. C. Jiao and A. H. Ayob reveal that national culture moderates the relationship between digitalization and trust, determining the specifics of the investment climate in different countries [12]. L. C. Backer analyzes digital «trust platforms» that transform corporate governance and transfer trust to a polycentric space [13]. O. Kowalewski and co-authors prove that institutional quality and cultural factors become the basis for the functioning of technologically oriented financial providers [14]. The generalization of this direction shows that digital trust has not only a legal, but also a socio-cultural nature, and further research should be directed at the formation of comparative models of digital trust in different cultural environments.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

Despite significant scientific progress in the study of digitalization and institutional trust, the issues of comprehensive assessment of their impact on the investment climate remain unresolved. The mechanisms of integrating digital tools with legal and institutional practices have not been sufficiently disclosed. There is a lack of empirical data to analyze the relationship between the state's digital maturity level and the stability of investment flows. The problems of cyber risks, unequal access to digital services, and legal uncertainty also remain essential.

The proposed research aims to address these gaps through a comprehensive analysis of the interdependence of digitalization and trust in institutions, systematization of problems that constrain investment activity, and formulation of practical recommendations. The use of interdisciplinary approaches and expansion of the empirical base will allow us to clarify patterns and develop new scientifically based solutions to increase the investment attractiveness of the economy.

Formulation of the article's objectives (task statement). The purpose of the article is to scientifically substantiate the relationship between digitalization and institutional trust as determining factors in the formation of a favorable investment

environment and to develop approaches to increasing the investment attractiveness of the national economy.

Research objectives:

1. To assess the level of digitalization of the economy and determine how its combination with institutional trust affects the formation of the investment climate.

1. To investigate the systemic interdependencies of digital transformations and trust in institutions, outlining the factors that constrain investment activity.

2. To develop practical recommendations for the integration of digital solutions and trust mechanisms into state investment policy.

Presentation of the research material. The current stage of economic development is marked by the rapid adoption of digital technologies, transforming not only business practices but also the mechanisms that shape the investment climate. Digitalization is becoming a key factor in the transparency, speed and reliability of economic processes, which significantly affects the trust of investors and their willingness to direct resources into national economies. The level of digital transformation determines the quality of the infrastructure for accessing information, the stability of financial transactions, the efficiency of administrative procedures and the ability to protect investments. As a result, a new paradigm of the investment climate is being formed, in which digital tools become not only an auxiliary resource but a fundamental element of ensuring competitiveness (table 1).

Table 1

The impact of digitalization of economic processes on the formation of the investment climate

Sphere of influence	Elements of digitalization	Expected effect on the investment climate
Financial transactions	Electronic payments, blockchain, fintech platforms	Reducing transaction costs, accelerating capital movement
Administrative services	Electronic government, online business registration	Simplifying procedures, increasing transparency and reducing corruption risks

Sphere of influence	Elements of digitalization	Expected effect on the investment climate
Information environment	Open data, digital analytics, big data	Availability of high-quality information for making investment decisions
Protection infrastructure	Cybersecurity, electronic identification	Increasing trust in the security of assets and contracts
Communication with investors	Digital platforms, CRM systems, and online forums	Operational interaction and forming a positive investment image of the country

Source: formed by the author based on [1; 2; 4, p. 389–390; 7, p. 3092–3093; 8; 9, p. 5250–5251]

The practical significance of digitalization for shaping the investment climate lies in the ability to combine technological solutions with institutional mechanisms of trust, reducing traditional barriers to market entry. The Ukrainian example of the Diia service demonstrates how digitalization can transform public administration in the field of entrepreneurship: in 2024, more than 400 thousand individual entrepreneurs were registered through the platform, and the average time to open a business decreased from several days to 15–30 min [15]. The e-Entrepreneur module, which was introduced in addition, combined ten key services for businesses, including changing KVEDs, tax services, and electronic reporting, thereby reducing the number of contacts with officials and significantly lowering corruption risks [16]. It indicates that digital deregulation not only reduces transaction costs but also forms an institutional environment in which investors receive predictability and stability of investment decisions.

International cases also confirm that digitalization is a direct factor in increasing attractiveness for investors. The e-Residency program in Estonia has enabled over 100,000 entrepreneurs from 176 countries to set up companies in European jurisdictions without a physical presence, which has brought additional tax revenues to the state and created a global image of a «digital state» [17]. At the same time, the level of penetration of digital solutions in Estonia has reached unique

proportions: 99% of government services are available online, and over 98% of banking transactions are carried out in digital format [18]. It proves that digital infrastructure is becoming a system-forming factor, without which competitiveness in the global investment market becomes impossible. Thus, digitalization works not as an auxiliary resource, but as a strategic driver of trust and predictability in investment processes. It creates conditions for a quick start of business, ensures transparency of regulatory procedures, guarantees the security of transactions and forms a new quality of the institutional environment. As a result, digital solutions serve as both an infrastructure for investment and a guarantee of sustainable economic development, as evidenced by the successes of the Ukrainian model and the practices of leading countries in digital transformations.

Institutional trust is a fundamental factor in the formation of a favorable investment environment, as it determines the level of predictability, security and stability of economic relations. Its presence ensures the legitimacy of government decisions, reduces transaction costs and contributes to the growth of long-term investments. In the context of modern crisis challenges, it is precisely trust in legal institutions, the judicial system, government bodies and independent regulators that determines the investor's willingness to invest, because without confidence in the impartiality and transparency of institutions, even the most attractive market with high profitability potential can remain risk-free only on paper. Studies by international organizations show that countries with a high level of trust in institutions have a more stable inflow of investment and a lower cost of attracting capital. In contrast, a lack of trust increases the risk premium and leads to an outflow of resources (table 2).

Table 2

The role of institutional trust in shaping the investment climate

Key aspect	Elements of institutional trust	Expected impact on investment
Legal certainty	Independence of the judicial system, effectiveness of contract law	Reducing the risk of non-performance of agreements, and

Key aspect	Elements of institutional trust	Expected impact on investment
		the predictability of investment decisions
Regulatory transparency	Accessibility and stability of legislation, absence of corruption	Increasing long-term investor confidence, increasing foreign direct investment
Institutional efficiency	Quality of regulators' work, fulfillment of state obligations	Reducing transaction costs and creating a positive image of the country
Social capital	Public trust in government and business, and the stability of public relations	Promoting the attraction of domestic and foreign investors
International standards	Compliance with OECD, EU, and World Bank practices	Increasing credit ratings, access to cheaper financial resources

Source: formed by the author based on [3, p. 74–75; 5, p. 57–58; 6, p. 380–381; 10; 11, p. 33–34]

The experience of the countries of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) confirms that a high level of trust in the government (over 60%) ensures a stable inflow of foreign direct investment and a decrease in the risk premium [19]. In Ukraine, despite the creation of the National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU) and the High Anti-Corruption Court as key elements of institutional trust, the legislative changes of 2025, which limited their autonomy, caused an adverse reaction from international partners and increased the riskiness of investments [20; 21]. In contrast, the experience of Estonia demonstrates that the combination of transparent justice and digital governance builds investor trust and ensures the stability of investments: in 2024, over 70% of companies confirmed that they make investment decisions based on trust in the institutional system [22]. In Latin American countries, where trust in the judiciary remains low, even active reforms and the digitalization of public services have failed to stop capital outflows: in 2022–2023, they exceeded \$15 billion [23]. It shows that in the absence of institutional trust, digitalization and other structural reforms are not able to guarantee sustainable growth in the investment environment independently.

In the modern economy, it is important to analyze not only the very fact of the combination of digitalization and institutional trust, but also the specific mechanisms through which this interaction affects the investment climate. These channels facilitate the transmission of effects, ranging from data transparency and uniformity in administrative procedures to increased competition in procurement and reduced operational risks through digital identification. Each of these channels forms its own configuration of institutional effects, which together reduce risks, reduce costs and increase the predictability of investment decisions. It is the consideration of these channels that allows us to reveal how digital transformation directly strengthens institutional trust and creates the basis for increasing investment attractiveness (table 3).

Table 3

Channels through which digital transformation enhances institutional trust and investment attractiveness

Dimension of digital transformation	Trust-building mechanism	Institutional effect	Investment consequence
Open data and transparent registries	Verifiability of information, public control	Reduction of information asymmetry and opportunities for abuse	Lower risk premium, faster transactions
E-services and «seamless» procedures	Reproducibility and uniformity of administrative procedures	Less discretion, more predictability	Reduction of time/cost of market entry
E-procurement and open tenders	Publicity of bidding rules and results	More competition, less collusion	Budget savings, clearer signals for investors
E-identity and e-signature	Verifiability of entities and transactions	Better contract execution, lower operational risk	Expansion of financial/B2G services, scalability
Analytics and GovTech core	Data-driven policy monitoring	More stable decisions, timely corrections	More predictable regulatory track

Source: compiled by the author based on [4, p. 392–393; 9, p. 5255–5256; 12; 13, p. 820–821; 14]

Digital transformation affects the investment climate not only indirectly through increased transparency or reduced costs, but also through the creation of new formats of interaction between the state, business and investors. Each dimension of digitalization forms its own set of trust mechanisms: from reducing information asymmetry through open data to strengthening contractual discipline through electronic identification and signature. In international practice, the complexity of these channels determines the different levels of attractiveness of economies. Thus, according to the UN DESA E-Government Survey 2024, countries with a high level of digital public services (Estonia, Denmark) simultaneously demonstrate both higher indicators of trust in the government and lower investment risks [24]. The Ukrainian Prozorro system confirms that open tenders not only save budget resources but also create «entry points» for foreign companies to the market, reducing barriers to participation in public procurement [25; 26]. A similar effect is observed in the field of digital identification: integrated BankID and Mobile ID systems not only simplify financial transactions, but also increase the legal certainty of transactions, which, as the World Bank GovTech Maturity Index 2022 shows, directly correlates with the level of investment attractiveness [27]. At the same time, the results of the OECD Digital Government Index show that it is the degree of integration of digital platforms into the management system that determines the stability of the regulatory environment, which goes beyond the standard effect of «transparency» [28].

Thus, channel analysis allows us to understand that digitalization forms not only convenience and resource savings, but also an entire architecture of trust that ensures long-term stability of investment processes. In Ukrainian conditions, one of the key problems limiting the positive impact of digitalization on investment activity is the fragmentation of the digital infrastructure, which does not ensure full integration of state registers, tax and customs systems [1]. It leads to duplication of procedures, increases the risk of technical failures and increases business costs for

interaction with state authorities. Cybersecurity remains a critical barrier: the prevalence of cyberattacks, insufficient protection of personal data, and commercial information undermine trust in digital services and create additional risks for investors [8; 10]. The imperfection of the legal field is manifested in the lag of legislation from the pace of digital transformations, which causes legal uncertainty in matters of electronic contracts, smart agreements and digital assets [5, p. 57–58]. Unequal access to digital technologies is also problematic: the gap between large companies and small and medium-sized businesses in the ability to use digital tools deepens institutional asymmetry, complicating equal access to investment resources [3, p. 74–75]. Insufficient transparency of individual digital platforms contributes to the emergence of shadow schemes and reduces the quality of corporate governance [12; 13, p. 820–821]. The persistence of high levels of corruption risks, despite the introduction of electronic services, indicates that digital technologies without proper institutional control are not capable of radically changing the investment climate.

In addition, weak communication between the state and business on issues of digital reforms reduces the level of predictability of the regulatory environment, which affects long-term investment strategies [7, p. 3092–3093; 9, p. 5255–5256]. In conditions of military and post-war challenges, the instability of political institutions becomes an additional limitation, which, even with the presence of digital tools, creates the image of a high-risk jurisdiction.

Effective integration of digital tools and mechanisms for strengthening trust in public investment policy requires multi-vector solutions, focused simultaneously on technological modernization and institutional stability. First of all, it is advisable to create a single integrated digital ecosystem that would combine state registries, tax and customs services, an electronic procurement system and platforms for investors in a transparent chain of «data – analytics – management decision». It will reduce not only transaction costs, but also administrative and time costs for businesses, while minimizing the risks of bureaucratic abuse.

The development of cybersecurity requires special attention, including the implementation of national data protection standards, regular audits of information systems and international cooperation in the field of countering cyberattacks. At the same time, improving the regulatory framework should eliminate legal gaps in the use of electronic contracts, smart agreements and digital assets, providing investors with legal certainty and predictability.

An important direction is to support small and medium-sized businesses through accessible digital services and training programs, thereby reducing digital inequality and ensuring equal conditions for entering the investment market. The introduction of open data mechanisms and independent public monitoring, which build trust in government processes and create additional incentives for investors, remains no less relevant.

In the field of government communication, developing institutional channels of dialogue with businesses based on digital platforms is advisable. This approach allows for a prompt response to problems and proposals from investors, thereby increasing the transparency and flexibility of the regulatory environment. Finally, a long-term strategy should include a combination of digital innovations with reforms in the field of justice and anti-corruption policy, since only a comprehensive approach ensures a complex relationship between technologies and trust as a foundation for sustainable investment growth.

Conclusions. The study confirmed that digitalization and institutional trust are interrelated factors that determine the quality of the investment environment. Digital technologies provide transparency, speed and accessibility of economic processes, but without trust in state and market institutions, their effect remains limited. In turn, institutional trust cannot be formed without digital mechanisms of openness and control. It is their combination that creates the prerequisites for long-term investment stability.

Several problems have been identified that hinder the positive impact of digitalization: infrastructure fragmentation, legal uncertainty in the field of electronic contracts, cyber risks, unequal access of small businesses to digital services, the persistence of corrupt practices and weak communication between the state and business. These factors increase risks and reduce the predictability of investment decisions, especially in conditions of political and institutional instability.

The creation of a single digital ecosystem of state and business services, strengthening cyber protection, improving the legal framework for digital assets, supporting small and medium-sized businesses in digital transformation and developing mechanisms for open data and public control are recommended. A comprehensive combination of digital innovations with justice and anti-corruption policy reforms is a key condition for increasing investment attractiveness. Prospects for further research include the quantitative assessment of digitalization and trust's impact on the investment climate, developing integrated indicators of this impact, and adapting international experience to Ukrainian conditions to form a more effective investment policy.

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